

Addendum to Odonatologica 44 (3): 279-342

**Update of the Odonata fauna of Georgia,
southern Caucasus ecoregion**

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Addendum. In the study by SCHRÖTER et al. (2015) the presentation of *Crocothemis erythraea* is erroneously missing in the species list. Data on *C. erythraea* is to be added and presented results adjusted accordingly. On page 279, the first sentence of the abstract therefore is to be corrected the following way:

A total of 64 odonate taxa were recorded in Georgia during nationwide surveys in June–July 2014, and June and July–August 2015, corresponding to at least 85 % of the country's Odonata fauna.

The same holds for the first sentence of the results, presented on page 289, which should read:

Altogether, 64 odonate taxa were recorded at 99 sampling sites (Fig. 1) corresponding at least 85 % of the Georgian Odonata fauna.

In the list of recorded species and taxa, on page 297 number 47 should pertain to *Crocothemis erythraea* (Brullé, 1832) instead of *Libellula depressa*; accordingly, the numbers of all following species are to be increased by one.

47. *Crocothemis erythraea* (Brullé, 1832)

2014: loc. 7 – A I; loc. 11 – A II; loc. 19 – A III; loc. 22 – A I; loc. 25 – AO V; loc. 29 – A II; loc. 34 – A II; loc. 36 – A I; loc. 43 – A I; loc. 51 – A IV; loc. 58 – ACO VI; loc. 65 – A II; loc. 69 – A II; loc. 71 – ACO IX; loc. 83 – A II.

Specimens 2014: loc. 19 – adult 1 ♀; loc. 11 – adults 1 ♂ 1 ♀; loc. 25 – adults 3 ♂ 2 ♀; loc. 58 – adults 6 ♂ 3 ♀, exuviae 2 ♂ 1 ♀; loc. 65 – adults 3 ♂; loc. 71 – exuviae 2 ♂ 2 ♀.

SCHRÖTER A., SEEHAUSEN M., KUNZ B., GÜNTHER A., SCHNEIDER T. & JÖDICKE R. 2015. Update of the Odonata fauna of Georgia, southern Caucasus ecoregion. *Odonatologica* 44: 279-342